

Indigenous knowledge of the '*Bawalis*' residing in the Sundarbans Delta: Survival strategy, resilience and adaptation to climate change driven from Antarctica

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Abstract

Near 3 million '*Bawalis*' (woodcutters) live in the Sundarbans Delta of Bangladesh and they live on the natural resources of the mangrove. The nomenclature of '*Bawalis*' was derived from '*Bauls*' (spiritual protector) and they ask the help of '*Bauls*' for protection against natural hazards. The '*Bawalis*' live an isolated life away from the mainstream. Their traditional knowledge acquired over the generations in adaptation to climate change is not well documented. The study attempted to do so in a scientific manner. This empirical study utilized only primary data. The '*Bawalis*' believe that the holy forests can protect the people from natural calamities. They also believe that God washes the forest twice a day and maintains its sanctity through tidal inundation. Clear felling and destruction of the natural regenerations are heinous sins. God allows only the extraction of non-wood products from the mangrove forests. True worship of the mangrove can only save the community from the sea level rise, tidal surges, tropical cyclones and other calamities. It is revealed that their beliefs and traditional knowledge are in line with SDG-13 and SDG-15. The study advocates for linking their knowledge with everyday science and acceptance by researchers and policymakers. Proper documentation, promotion, nurturing, and mainstreaming of their knowledge in national plans, roadmaps, strategies and policies are necessary through continuous research and development.

Keywords: Climate change, indigenous knowledge, *Sundarbans* delta, *Bawalis*, survival strategy, resilience, adaptation

Introduction

The Sundarbans Delta in Bangladesh is experiencing both predictable and unpredictable climate change impacts every year (Khan 2019, Chowdhury *et al.* 2020; Haque *et al.* 2020; Ali *et al.* 2019; Hasnat *et al.* 2020; Chiba *et al.* 2017; Alam *et al.* 2020; Billah 2018; Dastagir 2015; Rahman 2020; Rahman 2021; Rahman *et al.* 2021, Rahman 2022 a, b). Sea level rise, increased salinity and frequent tropical cyclones have become very familiar to the community (Rahman 2023 a, b, c, d, e). Most of the rivers of Bangladesh flow from north to south, silting up the mangrove delta and draining into the Bay of Bengal. The mangrove is a transitional territory between the freshwater rivers originating from the Ganges and the Bay of Bengal. Climate change poses a high risk to the ecosystems and landmass of this delta. The major threats are high levels of salinity, sedimentation, cyclones, storm surges, water logging and land erosion (Kaiser 2023).

Figure 1: Major threats due to climate change

Near 3 million 'Bawalis' (woodcutters) live in the Sundarbans Delta of Bangladesh and they live on the natural resources of the mangrove. The nomenclature of 'Bawalis' was derived from 'Bauls' (spiritual protector) and they ask the help of 'Bauls' for protection against natural hazards.

Figure 2: The characteristics of the ‘Bawalis’

The ‘Bawalis’ live an isolated life away from the mainstream. Their traditional knowledge acquired over the generations in adaptation to climate change is not well documented. The study attempted to do so in a scientific manner and to apply this knowledge in the survival strategy, resilience and adaptation to climate change.

Figure 3: Methodological framework

The study is qualitative and empirical data was used. A total number of 120 ‘Bawalis’ were personally interviewed with a semi-structured questionnaire. Content analysis was done to analyze the data.

Application of traditional knowledge in the coping mechanism

<i>Traditional knowledge</i>	<i>Scientific explanation</i>	<i>Coping mechanism</i>
The holy forests can protect the people from natural calamities	The mangrove works as a greenbelt against tropical cyclones	Mitigation

God washes the forest twice a day and maintains its sanctity through tidal inundation	The succession of a mangrove and the importance of its conservation	Mitigation
Clear felling and destruction of the natural regenerations are heinous sins	Clear felling and destruction of natural regenerations are the major threats to conservation	Mitigation
Keep faith in God and be brave during calamities	The principle of absorbing the shock	Resilience
Try to live with whatever you have	The principle of adaptation	Adaptation

Conclusions

Their beliefs and traditional knowledge are in line with SDG-13 and SDG-15. The study advocates for linking their knowledge with everyday science and acceptance by researchers and policymakers. Proper documentation, promotion, nurturing, and mainstreaming of their knowledge in national plans, roadmaps, strategies and policies are necessary through continuous research and development.

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